

Angelo Leogrando^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Ammonia Emissions in Europe

6% increased between 2010 and 2020

The Eurostat calculates the value of ammonia emissions in Europe. The indicator measures the amount of ammonia emissions (NH₃) following agricultural production. This value includes manure management. Ammonia emissions per hectare are calculated using the total agricultural area used (UAA) of the year pertinent as a denominator. The data on the EAA derive from the annual statistics of Eurostat crops.

Ranking of countries by value of ammonia emissions per hectare in 2020 in Europe. Turkey is in the first place for the value of ammonia emissions per hectare in 2020 with an amount equal to 858,132 tons per hectare, followed by France with a value equal to 526,510 and Spain with an amount of 459,788 units. In the middle of the standings there are Portugal with an amount equal to 51,776 tons per hectare, followed by Switzerland with a value of 49,161 and Sweden with an amount of 45,168 tons per hectare. Iceland closes the ranking with an amount of 4,328 tons per hectare, followed by Malta with an amount of 1,319 tons per hectare and Liechtenstein with an amount of 93 tons per hectare.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of ammonia emissions between 2010 and 2020. Turkey is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of ammonia emissions between 2010 and 2020 with an amount of 61.85% equal to an amount of 327,918 tons per hectare, followed by Bulgaria with an amount of 18.52% equal to an amount of 5,785 tons per hectare, Spain with an amount of 12.78% equal to a value of 52,110 tons per hectare. In the middle of the standings there are Sweden with an amount of -2.4% equal to an amount of -1,112 tons per hectare, followed by Italy with an amount of -3.69% equal to an amount of -12,719 tons per hectare, followed by Norway with an amount of -3.86% equal to an amount of -1,049 tons per hectare. Germany closes the ranking with an amount of -14.63% equal to an amount of -78,319 tons per hectare, followed by Finland with an amount of -17.39% equal to an amount of -5,771 tons per hectare, and from Malta with an amount of -18.88% equal to a value of -307 tons per hectare.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is the clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Specifically, four Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Latvia, Slovenia, Estonia, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Iceland, Slovakia, Croatia, Norway, Malta, Liechtenstein, Finland, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Sweden, Portugal, Switzerland,
- Cluster 2: France, Türkiye, Germany;
- Cluster 3: Italy, Poland, Spain;
- Cluster 4: Netherlands, Ireland, Denmark, Romania, Belgium, Czech Republic, Hungary, Austria, Greece,

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Below is the system of the Clusters for the value of the median with an amount of $C2 = 562.510 > C3 = 332.264 > C4 = 66.375 > C1 = 50.468$. From a geographical point of view, it is possible to note that the countries of northern Europe have a value of the production of ammonia for very limited hectare.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. Below are the network structures built through the application of the Euclidean distance. Specifically, structures are identified with complex networks and simplified network structures.

There is a complex network structure as indicated below:

- Austria has a connection with Hungary for an amount of 0.043 units;
- Hungary has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.038 units, and with Austria with an amount of 0.043 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Hungary for an amount of 0.038 units.

There is the following complex network structure or:

- Slovakia has a connection with Croatia for an amount of 0.044 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.037 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Slovakia for an amount of 0.044 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.037 units;
- Norway has a connection with Croatia for an amount of 0.037 units and with Slovakia for a value of 0.027 units.

There is the following complex network structure:

- Estonia has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.019 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.019 units and with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.036 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.036 units and with the Island for an amount of 0.01 units;
- Iceland has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.01 units and with mortar for a value of 0.089 units;
- Malta has a connection with Iceland for an amount of 0.089 units and with Liechtenstein for an amount of 0.016 units;
- Liechtenstein has a connection with Malta for an amount of 0.016 units.

There are also simplified network structures or:

- Sweden and Portugal have a connection for an amount of 0.034 units;
- Lithuania and Bulgaria have a connection for an amount of 0.022 units;
- Denmark and Belgium have a connection for an amount of 0.041 units.

Conclusions. Ammonia emissions are increased in Europe between 2010 and 2020 on average for countries considered by about 6% or 7,350 tons per hectare. However, it must be considered that in most countries considered the value of ammonia emissions, it decreased between 2010 and 2020. However, there are some countries where this value grew abundantly as for example in Turkey where a value of +61.85%, in Bulgaria with an amount of 18.52%, and in Spain with +12.78%. However, if Turkey is eliminated from the sample, it is possible to verify that the value of the production of ammonia on average for European countries between 2010 and 2020 has decreased by an amount equal to -3%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

C2>C3>C4>C1

